

RDA's 23 Things for RDM adopted: a new tool for info and training amongst different audiences

Cees Hof & Fieke Schoots

Representing the *23 Things task group* of the
(Dutch) National Coordination Point Research Data Management (LCRDM)

cees.hof@dans.knaw.nl & f.schoots@library.leidenuniv.nl

LCRDM Netwerkdag
November 3, 2020

Adopting 23 Things ... from RDA to LCRDM

What?

23 Things versions for different audiences

Why?

- New topics for Dutch context: FAIR, GDPR, LCRDM, Open Science...
- We need common understanding of RDM among diverse practitioners and supporters

How?

Via a RDA adoption grant, a Dutch LCRDM task group and community sprints (June '19 - September '20)

Deliverables

All deliverables available via: <https://www.lcrdm.nl/23things>

23 Things: Libraries for Research Data
An overview of practical, free, online resources and tools that you can begin using today to incorporate research data management into your practice of librarianship.

RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

Research Data Sharing Without Barriers

Learning Resources

Librarians are learning how to apply the principles of library science to solve problems and to provide new services related to research data.

1. A "top ten" list of recommendations for libraries to get started with research data management from LIBER, <http://bit.ly/RDAthings1>
2. Relevant concepts are presented and mapped in the e-Science Thesaurus, <http://bit.ly/RDAthingz>
3. Understanding the life of research data with the DCC Curation Lifecycle Model,

Learning Resources
 Data Reference and Outreach
 Data Management Plans
 Data Literacy
 Citing Data
 Data Licensing and Privacy
 Digital Preservation
 Data Repositories
 and a Community of Practice

...to help librarians engage in research data management!

Data Reference & Outreach

Librarians are answering questions about data from patrons and conducting outreach to assess the data needs of their researchers and

10. Questions about data answered by experts on the DataQ forum, <http://bit.ly/RDAthing10>

Data Management Plans

Librarians are becoming familiar with funder requirements and consulting with researchers to help them write and implement effective data management plans.

11. One example is the DMPTool that lists funder requirements in the United States and builds a plan by asking the researcher to answer a series of questions. Other countries such as the U.K. and Canada have similar tools, <http://bit.ly/RDAthing11>

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/23-things-libraries-research-data-rdas-libraries-research-data-interest-group.html>

RDM audiences

- Researcher
- Student
- Librarian
- Data Steward
- IT Staff
- Research Software Engineer
- Policy Maker

National **Coordination Point**
Research Data Management

The process ...

National **Coordination Point**
Research Data Management

Lessons learned: highlights

Community

- Motivating community effort, strengthen relation between Dutch community and RDA, new initiatives (Dutch Network for Training on Research Data & Coding)

Tool

- Other communities can adopt the tool if we share the code and recognise the tool as an RDA outcome

Method

- The sprint method was challenging at first but participants showed a great commitment. Idea of a tool was raised during the sessions, and embraced with such enthusiasm that it couldn't be ignored.

Looking into the future.....

To avoid:

Maintenance Plan

- Editorial board, maintenance

Communication and Dissemination plan

Training plan

- Ready to use training packages/modules
- Embed in existing RDM courses, like Essentials 4 Data Support

Expand involved community

Get our sustainability act together....

National **Coordination Point**
Research Data Management

The output.....

Digital sheets for training purposes

- Things for researchers & PhD candidates
- Things for Bachelor & Master students
- Things for data & subject librarians
- Things for data stewards
- Things for IT support staff & IT specialists
- Things for research software engineers
- Things for policy makers

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3773663>

The output.....

A Tool based on an interactive site & underlying database!

Filter by:

Audience (7 options)

Theme (16 options)

Type (12 options)

Data life cycle (6 options)

<https://23things.sites.uu.nl> (beta)

Using the Tool!

A (simplified) user story....

Boris:

- 1) Is a data steward at the TU Eindhoven
- 2) A PhD student, writing her thesis, asked him how she should cite the code/software that she received from her professor for doing her analysis....

National **Coordination Point**
Research Data Management

Boris selects his audience...

National Coordination Point Research Data Management

Audience

- Bachelor & Master Students (20)
- Data & Subject Librarians (59)
- Data Stewards (63)
- IT Support Staff & Specialists (21)
- Policy Makers (45)
- Research Software Engineers (36)
- ✓ Researchers & PhD Candidates (45)**

Type
Data life cycle

App for Privacy and Security

Check out the Erasmus University's Privacy and Security app

Compliance, Ethics, Privacy & Data Licensing

Checklist for assessment of FAIR

Use this checklist for assessment of FAIRness of your data

Metadata

Data life cycle examples from JISC

Understand the life of research data

Data Management Plans
Learning Resources

Define personal sensitive data

See for sensitive data

Compliance & Licensing

Describe the data

Example of how to enable software

Example of turning data into scientific data

Example of data

Boris selects his theme...

**National Coordination Point
Research Data Management**
(The Netherlands)

RESEARCH

Researchers & PhD Ca Theme Data life cycle

- Citing Data & Code (2)
- Community of Practice (2)
- Compliance, Ethics, Privacy & Data Licensing (11)
- Data Management Plans (7)
- Data Repositories (3)
- Learning Resources (6)
- Metadata (11)
- Outreach (2)
- Policy Development (1)
- Setting the Scene (2)

App for Privacy and Security
Check out the Erasmus University Privacy and Security app
Compliance, Ethics, Privacy & Data Licensing

Data life cycle examples from JISC
Understand the life of research data
Data Management Plans
Learning Resources

Describe the data

Example of how to enable software

Example of turning data into scientific

Boris gets two possible solutions...

**National Coordination Point
Research Data Management**
(The Netherlands)

RESEARCH

Researchers & PhD Ca | **Citing Data & Code (2)** | Type | Data life cycle

Example of how to enable software citation

Learn how to enable citation of your software

Citing Data & Code

Promote the scientific value of data and code

Learn how to cite data and code in publications

Citing Data & Code

One of the “Things”
providing info on
software citation...

FAIR Software Route
<https://fair-software.eu>

F A I R 1 2 3 4 5 ENDORSE

#4
ENABLE CITATION OF { & }
THE SOFTWARE

2 1 3

WHY THIS IS IMPORTANT HELP ME CHOOSE

Or....design your own learning path!

The screenshot shows the website for the National Coordination Point Research Data Management (The Netherlands). The header includes a navigation menu with 'Partners' and 'About'. The main content area features a search bar with filters for 'Data Stewards (4)', 'Data Management Pla', 'RDM tool (4)', and 'planning (4)'. Below the search bar are four content cards, each titled 'Resources for reviewing and assessing DMPs' and containing the text 'Review and/or assess the data management plans written by your researchers'. Each card also has a 'Data Management Plans' button at the bottom. The fourth card is highlighted with a yellow border.

23 Things Revisited: Field guides to research data management, an adoption project

(original project title)

Remarks, suggestions, additions?

Want to add your own Things to the tool?

Please mail: info@lcrdm.nl

TIME FOR QUESTIONS!

National **Coordination Point**
Research Data Management